

This expectation has fully been realised.

The condensation takes place smoothly at the room temperature between equimolecular quantities of the reactants in alcoholic medium. The hydrazo-compounds (I or III) thus obtained give characteristic colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid, and are found to be affected by light and air. They give rise to mono-acetyl derivatives with great ease and are oxidised by ferric chloride to the corresponding azo compounds (V). The azo compounds give colour reactions characteristic of the respective hydrazo-compounds and are reconverted into the original hydrazo compounds by the action of zinc dust and acetic acid. Thus :

The hydrazo-compounds (I or III) are easily transformed into the isomeric bases (II or IV), when boiled with dilute hydrochloric acid for a few minutes.

The results of this investigation when considered along with those recorded by Pyman and his collaborators and by Bose lend support to the view put forward by Fargher and Pyman in the case of the glyoxaline derivatives, namely that the condition which essentially determines the isomeric change is the linking between the carbon atoms that are involved in a change of the benzidine type. In other words, a conjugated system of double bonds which connects the 1 and 4 carbon atoms of a benzene nucleus must be present in a heterocyclic ring before the latter can qualify for the isomeric change. In the case of the thiazole ring in formula (I or

III), it will be seen that the 2- and 5-carbon atoms are connected by alternate single and double bonds and as such they behave like hydrazo-benzene.

The next attempt was to condense 1-*p*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide with halogenated ketones. In this case it was expected that if the condensation occurred normally, the products having a *para*-substituted nucleus would suffer semidine change under the influence of mineral acids (*cf.* Michaelis and Schäfer, *Annalen*, 1915, 407, 229) thus :

The condensation of 1-*p*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide with halogenated ketones proceeded smoothly at the room temperature. The products, however, on boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid, split off ammonia and were converted into keto-compounds. To understand the nature of such a change it is necessary at this stage to indicate the various possibilities, which an 1-substituted-thiosemicarbazide (having various reactive centres) presents during condensation with a halogenated ketone. In fact one can expect besides (VI) as many as four different products* of condensation, namely—

* For the formulation of these compounds the halogen of the ketone has been supposed to be eliminated with the "thiol" hydrogen of the thiosemicarbazide. This is followed by ring closure. That the "thio" part is more reactive towards halogenated ketones than the imino or amino groups has been supported by the researches of Dixon and Taylor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2502), of Walther and Roch (*J. pr. Chem.* 1913, (ii), 87, 27), of Bose (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 51), and others.

Of these only (IX) and (X) can give rise to keto compounds with simultaneous formation of ammonia by hydrolysing agents. In one case (IX) the resulting product would be an 1:3:4-thiodiazine (XII) and in the other case (X), a thiazole (XIII).

The keto compounds were found to be quite stable and were insoluble in caustic alkalis. This evidence seems to be in favour of the formula (XIII) for the keto compound. Consequently the condensation products should be represented by (X).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of 1-o-Tolylthiosemicarbazide.—*o*-Tolylhydrazine (12.2 gms.), freshly prepared alcoholic hydrochloric acid (prepared by passing 3.65 gms. of dry hydrochloric acid gas through 20 c.c. of absolute alcohol in the cold), and potassium sulphocyanide (14.55 g.) were heated on a water-bath under reflux for nearly 12 hours. The contents of the flask, on cooling, were poured into cold water and a solid mass separated which was collected and washed with water several times. The product was finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 163-64°. It is easily soluble in cold acetone, alcohol and pyridine but insoluble in water. Yield, 9 gms. (Found: N, 23.3. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires N, 23.2 per cent.).

2-o-Tolylhydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula I, $\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$).

Finely powdered 1-*o*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide (9 g.) and ω -bromo-acetophenone (1 gm.) were shaken with 10 c.c. of absolute alcohol at the room temperature, without application of heat. The components gradually dissolved with evolution of heat. After about 15 minutes, the hydrobromide of the base crystallised out. Nearly 5 c.c. of pyridine were then added, when the crystals dissolved. On diluting with water white crystals of the free base separated out. These were collected, washed with water and dilute alcohol and dried. The yield of the crude product was 1.5 gms. It was

finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale brown needles, m.p. 175°–180° with decomposition. (Found: N, 14.62. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14.95 per cent.).

The substance gives a blue colouration with conc. sulphuric acid; the colour vanishes on dilution. It turns brown when kept exposed to air. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, pyridine but insoluble in water.

Acetyl derivative —The acetyl derivative was obtained by heating the base with acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine for a few minutes. It was crystallised twice from dilute alcohol in white star-like aggregates, m.p. 152°. (Found: N, 18.12. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_3S$ requires N, 18.01 per cent.).

2-o Tolylo-azo-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula V, R = Ph).

2-o Tolylohydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole (1 gm) was taken up with 5 c.c. of alcohol and nearly 2 gm. of ferric chloride were added to it. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for nearly two hours under reflux. The contents were cooled and about 2 c.c. of conc. hydrochloric acid were added. On diluting the contents of the flask with cold water, orange coloured crystals separated out. This was re-crystallised from dilute alcohol in beautiful orange plates with a golden lusture, m.p. 110°. It is slightly soluble in water and easily soluble in alcohol, pyridine and acetone. It dyes wool a yellow shade and gives deep blue coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid. It refused acetylation. (Found: N, 15.15. $C_{16}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 15.07 per cent.).

It gave, on reduction with zinc dust and dilute acetic acid, the hydrazo compound from which it had been derived.

In this connection it has been found that the hydrazo compounds described by Bose (*loc. cit.*) which are also similarly constituted are oxidised by ferric chloride under the conditions stated above to the corresponding azo-compounds. Thus, 2-phenylhydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole is oxidised to 2-benzene-azo-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole which forms bright orange needles, m.p. 117°. It dyes wool yellow shade (Found: N, 15.84. $C_{15}H_{11}N_3S$ requires N, 15.85 per cent.).

2-Phenyl-hydrazino-4-p-tolyl-1:3-thiazole gave 2-benzene-azo-4-p-tolyl-1:3-thiazole, which forms small prismatic crystals of deep orange colour from dilute alcohol, m.p. 161°. It dyes wool deep orange shade. (Found: N, 15.08. $C_{16}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 15.07 per cent.).

2-Phenylhydrazino-4-methyl-1:3 thiazole was similarly oxidised to 2-benzene-azo-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole. This was obtained from dilute alcohol in small orange crystals, m. p. 120°. It dyes wool yellow shade (Found: N, 20·67. $C_{10}H_9N_3S$ requires N, 20·7 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on 2-o-Tolyldiazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole: Formation of 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-p-amino (m)-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula II, R = Ph).

2-o-Tolyldiazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole (1·5 gm.) was boiled with nearly 100 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:4) till the former dissolved completely. The solution was allowed to cool, filtered and made alkaline with ammonia. A white mass separated out. This was collected, washed with water and crystallised with the aid of animal charcoal as decoloriser from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m. p. 165°. It did not respond to the colour reaction characteristic of its isomeride. It is readily soluble in pyridine, acetone, alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: N, 15·21. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14·93 per cent.).

The hydrochloride crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in white needles, m. p. 197°. It was dried in air and finally over sulphuric acid in a desiccator. It is easily soluble in water and alcohol but moderately in acetone. (Found: Cl, 19·19. $C_{16}H_{17}N_3S \cdot Cl_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires Cl, 19·1 per cent.).

The picrate was prepared by adding to the saturated solution of the base in alcohol, a saturated solution of picric acid in dilute alcohol. It was crystallised finally from dilute acetone in reddish yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 227° with decomposition. (Found: N, 16·53. $C_{22}H_{16}O_6N_6S$ requires N, 17·07 per cent.).

Diacetyl derivative.—On adding acetic anhydride to 2-amino-4-phenyl-5p--amino-(m)-tolyl-1:3-thiazole, the latter dissolved with evolution of heat. The solution was boiled for sometime and then on pouring the solution into cold water, a crystalline product separated out. It was recrystallised from dilute alcohol, by the aid of animal charcoal as decoloriser, in white rectangular crystals, m. p. 182°. (Found: N, 11·41. $C_{20}H_{19}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 11·51 per cent.).

The chloroplatinate was prepared by adding platinum chloride to an alcoholic solution of the base. The product was purified by washing with water and dilute alcohol. It formed dull yellow microscopic crystals, which did not melt below 300°. (Found: Pt, 27·17. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S \cdot H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 27·51 per cent.).

2-o-Tolylhydrazino-4-p-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula I, R=p-Tolyl).

From 0.9 gm. of *o*-tolylthiosemicarbazide and 1 gm. of *p*-methyl-*w*-bromacetophenone, 1.6 gm. of the crude product were obtained. The method of preparation was identical with that described under the corresponding phenyl compound (p. 646). It was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and dilute alcohol in pale brown shining plates, which melt with decomposition at 179°. (Found: N, 14.6. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.23 per cent.).

It is easily soluble in acetone, alcohol, and pyridine and insoluble in water. It gives a green colour with concentrated sulphuric acid, which vanishes on dilution.

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from dilute acetone in fine white needles, m. p. 160°-161°. (Found: N, 12.45. $C_{19}H_{19}ON_3S$ requires N, 12.47 per cent.).

2-o-Tolyl-azo-4-p-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula V, R=p-Tolyl).

Obtained by oxidising the hydrazo compound with alcoholic ferric chloride solution it formed brick-red crystals (from dilute alcohol), m. p. 148°. It could be reduced to the original hydrazo compound with zinc dust and acetic acid. (Found: N, 14.62. $C_{17}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14.32 per cent.).

It gives a green coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid.

Action of Hydrochloric acid on 2-o-Tolyl-hydrazino-4-p-tolyl-1:3-thiazole: Formation of 2-Amino-4-p-tolyl-5-p-amino-(m)-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula II, R=p-Tolyl).

The base (1 gm.) gave, on being boiled with 100 c.c. of 2.5N hydrochloric acid, 0.6 gm. of the diamine. It crystallised from a mixture of dilute alcohol and pyridine in pale brown needles, m.p. 181°. It is readily soluble in alcohol, acetone, and pyridine and insoluble in water. (Found: N, 14.52. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14.23 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol (animal charcoal used as decoloriser) in white rectangular crystals, m.p. 208°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone and pyridine but insoluble in water. (Found: N, 10.94. $C_{21}H_{21}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 11.09 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* of the base crystallised from hydrochloric acid in small shining crystals, m.p. 278° with decomposition. It

was dried first by exposing it to the air and then in a desiccator over sulphuric acid. (Found: Cl, 19.28. $C_{17}H_{19}N_3S$ requires Cl, 19.28 per cent.).

The *chloroplatinate* of the base was obtained in dull brown microscopic crystals which did not melt below 300° by adding an aqueous solution of platinum chloride to a saturated solution of the base in alcohol. It was purified by washing with water and dilute alcohol. (Found: Pt, 27.7. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S, H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 27.67 per cent.).

It is slightly soluble in alcohol, acetone and pyridine but insoluble in water.

The *picrate* formed yellow crystals, m.p. 201° (decomp.). (Found: N, 16.26. $C_{23}H_{18}O_6N_6S$ requires N, 16.6 per cent.)

2-o-Tolylhydrazino-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula I, $R=CH_3$).

The product (1.5 gm.) from 1-*o*-tolylthiosemicarbazide (1.8 g.) and chloroacetone (1 gm. in 15 c.c. alcohol) crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and dilute alcohol in reddish needles which melted and decomposed at 162° . It is insoluble in water but readily soluble in alcohol, acetone and pyridine. It turned red on exposure to air and light. The substance imparts a pink colour to concentrated sulphuric acid; the colour vanishes on dilution. (Found: N, 19.3. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 19.2 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from dilute acetone, using animal charcoal as a decoloriser, in beautiful white rectangular plates, m.p. 96° . (Found: N, 16.44. $C_{13}H_{15}ON_3S$ requires N, 16.11 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on 2-o-Tolylhydrazino-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole: Formation of 2-Amino-4-methyl-5-p-amino-(m)-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula II, $R=CH_3$).

It was first crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and dilute alcohol (animal charcoal used), and then from dilute acetone in pale brown needles, which turned brown on coming in contact with air and light, melting at 144° . It is easily soluble in acetone, alcohol, pyridine but insoluble in water and benzene. It did not respond to the colour reaction characteristic of its isomer. (Found: N, 19.59. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 19.17 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid in colourless stout needles, m.p. 261° with decomposition.

The *diacetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute acetone in long prismatic needles, m. p. 286°. (Found: N, 14.26. $C_{15}H_{17}N_3$ SO₂ requires N, 13.87 per cent.).

The *picrate* formed yellow crystals (from dilute acetone) with a golden lustre. It begins to decompose at 200° and melts at 247° with complete decomposition. (Found: N, 19.36. $C_{17}H_{13}O_6N_6S$ requires N, 19.6 per cent.).

The *chloroplatinate* of the base formed dull grey microscopic crystals which did not melt below 300°. (Found: Pt, 80.24. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt, 30.97 per cent.).

Preparation of 1-m-Tolylthiosemicarbazide.

The preparation of this compound is very similar to that of the *ortho*-compound. The product crystallised in white plates, m. p. 134-35°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone and pyridine (yield, 9 gms. from 12.2 gms. of *m*-tolylhydrazine). (Found: N, 23.12. $C_8H_{11}N_3S$ requires N, 23.2 per cent.)

2-m-Tolylhydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula III, R=Ph).

ω -Bromo-acetophenone (2 g.) and 1-*m*-tolylthiosemicarbazide (1.8 g.) and 15 c.c. of absolute alcohol were taken. The procedure is similar to that described under 2-*o*-tolylhydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole. The product was purified by crystallisation from dilute pyridine. It formed white needle-shaped crystals, m. p. 188° with decomposition. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, acetic acid, pyridine.

It gives a blue coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid (yield, 3 gm.). (Found: N, 14.93. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14.95 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m. p. 145°. It is soluble in acetone, acetic acid, alcohol and pyridine. (Found: N, 13.06. $C_{18}H_{17}N_3SO$ requires N, 13.01 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on 2-m-Tolyl-hydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole: Formation of 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-p-amino-(o)-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula IV, R=Ph).

The product was crystallised from dilute acetone in pale brown needles, m. p. 185°. It is soluble in acetone, acetic acid, alcohol, pyridine and insoluble in water. It does not give any colour re-

action with concentrated sulphuric acid. Yield, quantitative. (Found: N, 14·85. $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 14·95 per cent.)

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in white crystals, m. p. 265°-270° with decomposition. (Found: Cl, 19·45. $C_{16}H_{17}N_3Cl_2S$, H_2O requires Cl, 19·1 per cent.)

2-Acetylamino-4-phenyl-5-p-acetylamino-(o)-tolyl-1: 3-thiazole was prepared as usual. From dilute acetone, using animal charcoal as decoloriser, it was obtained as white stout crystals, m. p. 235°. (Found: S, 8·85. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_3S$ requires S, 8·77 per cent.)

The *picrate* was crystallised from dilute acetone in yellow prismatic crystals, m. p. 215° with decomposition.

2-m-Tolylhydrazino-4-p-tolyl-1: 3-thiazole (Formula III, R=*p*-Tolyl).

The procedure was identical with that described for *2-m-tolylhydrazino-4-phenyl-1: 3-thiazole*. 1·8 Gms. of *1-m-tolylthiosemicarbazide*, 2·13 gms. of *p-methyl-w-bromo-acetophenone* and 15 c.c. of absolute alcohol were taken. The free base (3 gms.) crystallised from dilute pyridine in pale brown needles, m. p. 191° with decomposition. It is soluble in acetone, acetic acid, alcohol and pyridine but insoluble in water. It gives a green colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. It turns brown on exposure to air and light. (Found: S, 10·97. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires S, 10·85 per cent.)

The *acetyl derivative* crystallised from dilute acetone in white crystals, m. p. 121°. (Found: N, 12·69. $C_{19}H_{19}N_3SO$ requires N, 12·47 per cent.)

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on 2-m-Tolyl-hydrazino-4-p-tolyl-1: 3-thiazole: Formation of 2-Amino-4-p-tolyl-5-p-amino-(o)-tolyl-1: 3-thiazole (Formula IV, R=*p*-Tolyl).

The diamine formed pale brown needles, m. p. 175°.

It is soluble in alcohol, pyridine, acetone and acetic acid and insoluble in water. It does not give colour reaction with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 14·39. $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 14·23 per cent.)

The *acetyl derivative* crystallised from dilute acetone, using animal charcoal as decoloriser, in stout needles, m. p. 248°. (Found: N, 11·12. $C_{21}H_{21}N_3SO_2$ requires N, 11·09 per cent.)

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in stout white crystals, m. p. 247°. (Found: Cl, 19.45. $C_{17}H_{19}N_3SCl_2$ requires Cl, 19.28 per cent.)

The *picrate* formed yellow needles, m. p. 202° (from dilute alcohol).

2-n-Tolylhydrazino-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula III, $R=CH_3$)

The method of preparation is similar to that adopted for 2-*o*-tolyl hydrazino-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole. 1.8 Gms. of 1-*m*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide and 1 gm. of monochloro-acetone and 15 c.c. of alcohol were taken. The product formed reddish needles from dilute pyridine, m.p. 135°, with decomposition. It is soluble in acetone, alcohol, pyridine, acetic acid and insoluble in water. It readily turns brownish red on exposure to air and light. Yield, 1.2 gms. It imparts a pink colour to conc. sulphuric acid, the colour vanishes on dilution with water. (Found: N, 18.86. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 19.2 per cent.)

Acetyl derivative.—It crystallised from dilute acetone, using animal charcoal as decoloriser, in colourless prismatic crystals, m.p. 119°. (Found: N, 16.09. $C_{13}H_{16}OSN_3$ requires N, 16.11 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on 2-m-Tolylhydrazino 4-methyl-1:3-thiazole: Formation of 2-Amino-4-methyl-5-p-amino-(o)-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula IV, $R=CH_3$).

The diamine formed yellow needles, m.p. 157°. It is soluble in acetone, alcohol, pyridine, acetic acid and insoluble in water. It gives no colour reaction with conc. sulphuric acid. Yield 60 per cent. (Found: N, 19.86. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 19.19 per cent.).

The *acetyl derivative* crystallised from dilute acetone in white plates, m.p. 236°. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{15}H_{17}N_3SO_2$ requires N, 13.87 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in fine white feathery needles, m.p. 263°, with decomposition.

The *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow crystals, m.p. 212°, with decomposition.

Preparation of 1-p-Tolylthiosemicarbazide.—Following the usual procedure, about 4.5 gms. of the product were obtained from 10 gms. of *p*-tolylhydrazine hydrochloride (in 40 c.c. of alcohol).

It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless hexagonal plates, m.p. 174°. The reported m.p. of this compound prepared by Pellizzari and Ferro (*Gazzetta*, 1898, **28**, ii, 560) is 150°. (Found: S, 17.6. $C_9H_{11}N_3S$ requires S, 17.68 per cent.)

It is easily soluble in acetone, pyridine or aqueous alkali but not in benzene. Attempts to improve the yield by carrying on the reaction in sealed tubes or by substituting ammonium sulphocyanide for the potassium salt were fruitless.

1-p-Tolylthiosemicarbazide and w-Bromo-acetophenone: Formation of 2-Imino-3-p-toluidino-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole (Formula X, R=Ph).

The condensation was carried out and the product isolated as in the case of 1-*o*-tolylthiosemicarbazide and *w*-bromo-acetophenone. The base crystallised from acetone in colourless needles, m.p. 193°, with decomposition. It is also soluble in pyridine, but only sparingly in alcohol. It gave a deep blue coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 14.98. $C_{16}H_{16}N_3S$ requires N, 14.95 per cent.)

Acetyl derivative.—It formed long colourless needles (from alcohol); m.p. 147°. (Found: C, 66.63. H, 5.34. $C_{18}H_{17}N_3SO$ requires C, 66.88, H, 5.26 per cent.)

2-Keto-3-p-toluidino-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole.
(Formula XIII, R=Ph.)

The imino compound described above (1.5 gm.) was boiled with 1.5 N-hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) for about half an hour and filtered hot from a small amount of orange insoluble matter. The filtrate was cooled and just made alkaline with caustic soda, when the solution turned milky and the smell of ammonia was noticeable. A pale yellow precipitate began to settle down very slowly. This was collected after a couple of hours, washed with cold water and dried (1.2 gm.). It freely dissolved in methyl or ethyl alcohol, acetone and dilute acids.

The substance was purified by crystallisation from benzene by the addition of ligroin. It formed transparent yellow plates, m.p. 210°-211°. It is insoluble in alkali. (Found: C, 67.59; H, 5.13; N, 10.18. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2S$ requires C, 68.08; H, 4.96; N, 9.93 per cent.)

2-Imino-3-p-toluidino-4-methyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole.(Formula X, R=CH₃).

The procedure for the condensation of 1-*o*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide and monochloroacetone was followed in this case. The base crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in reddish needles, m.p. 168-69°. (Found: C, 59.94; H, 6.02. C₁₁H₁₃N₃S requires C, 60.28; H, 5.94 per cent.).

The *p*-tolyl-thiocarbimide derivative crystallised from dilute acetone in pale brown needles, m.p. 143°. (Found: N, 15.22. C₁₃H₂₀N₄S₂ requires N, 15.22 per cent.).

2-Keto-3-p-toluidino-4-methyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole.(Formula XIII, R=CH₃).

The imino compound (0.7 gm.) was boiled with N-hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.) for about an hour. The brown precipitate obtained by neutralising the acid, crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol (animal charcoal used) in hard, pale yellow crystals, m.p. 177°. (Found: N, 12.87. C₁₁H₁₂ON₂S requires N, 12.73 per cent.).

2-Imino-3-p-toluidino-4-p-tolyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole.(Formula X, R=*p*-Tolyl.)

The condensation was carried out as in the case of 1-*o*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide and *p*-methyl-*w*-bromo-acetophenone, the yield being quantitative. The base crystallised from alcohol and pyridine in pale brown needles, m.p. 184°, with decomposition. (Found: N, 14.25. C₁₇H₁₇N₃S requires N, 14.24 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative formed glistening needles (from alcohol), m.p. 155°. (Found: N, 12.72. C₁₉H₁₉ON₃S requires N, 12.46 per cent.).

The *p*-tolyl-thiocarbimide derivative crystallised from dilute acetone in pale yellow, shining plates, m.p. 152°.

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